

RECENT DEVELOPMENTS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS OF CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Composite structures in ceramics have been developed for two major reasons. First they provide a means to enhance dramatically the performance of the so-called functional ceramics; these are systems where electrical, dielectric, piezoelectric or sensing properties are greatly amplified by appropriate composite design. Industrial applications are fully established. Secondly they are used to avoid or diminish the brittle behaviour of structural ceramic systems. Many methods have been attempted including particulate reinforcement and reinforcement with short fibres, whiskers or long fibres; the success of these methods has been variable.

In discussing progress in the structural ceramics sector, attention is given to three aspects:

(a) **Design.** Developments in laminar structures and in nanocomposite systems are examples which show the rich range of possibilities that is still open to designers in the search for toughened structures. It is now important to have procedures for design selection so that the optimal choice among the alternative opportunities can be made in the context of the conditions set by intended applications.

(b) **Processing.** Cost-effective and reliable production of composite systems remains a challenging theme where a greater diversity of approach would be rewarding. Classical ceramic methods and the chemical vapour infiltration route have been extensively developed; the current attention to *in situ* composite formation indicates, however, recognition of the limitations that exist in the available process methods and the needs that arise for alternative routes.

(c) **Characterisation.** With the excellent progress in the structural characterisation of composite systems, their phases and interfaces, it now becomes vital to link this understanding with corresponding characterisation of the damage mechanisms that are active in short and long-term loading conditions and in aggressive atmospheres at temperature.

The current availability on the one hand of precisely controlled methods for fabrication and testing and on the other hand of powerful procedures for modelling and simulation is an excellent basis for an effective and productive interaction between theory and experiment as systematic and cost-effective exploitation of ceramic matrix composites is undertaken.